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Management of Onion Rust through Host Resistance and Alternate Application of Fungicides in Adjara, Georgia

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Abstract

Onion (*Allium cepa*) is the most important vegetable among *Allium* crops in the world due to its nutritional and health benefits, attacked by many harmful Pathogens. The main objective of this study was to identify and determine the main pathogens of Onion evaluate the effects of integrated disease management through host resistance; alternate fungicide applications on rust epidemic and bulb yield; and determine the economics of fungicide application in the management of onion rust. Field experiments were conducted in Adjara (Khelvachauri and Keda), using 3 onion varieties, namely Creole, Pinoy F1 and Enza (local cultivar) Mancozeb and Nativo fungicides were sprayed with alternate and alone applications during the 2019/2022 cropping season. Treatments were arranged factorially in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Analyses of variance revealed that interaction effects of Mancozeb, Nativo, and their alternate applications with Pinoy F1 and Creole varieties showed the lowest disease severity, area under the disease progress curve, and disease progress rate as compared to the unsprayed plots of all varieties. The higher disease severity was recorded in 2020 than in 2019 cropping season. In Adjara (2019), the variety Pinoy F1 showed significantly higher (21.1 t ha⁻¹) yield and, exhibited 1.4 t and 6.0 t yield advantages over Creole variety and the local cultivar, respectively. However, there was no significant difference among the fungicides tested on bulb yield in both districts, but lower relative yield losses were recorded in response to application of Mancozeb and Nativo alone. In 2020 than the maximum net profit was obtained on the onion varieties Pinoy F1 and Creole in combination with Mancozeb fungicide alone and on the variety Local only with Nativo. In case of alternate fungicide applications, higher marginal rate of return was noted than on unprotected plots. Especially treatment of Pinoy F1 and Local cultivar with Mancozeb+Nativo indicated higher marginal rate of return value than Nativo+Mancozeb and unsprayed plots.

Keywords: onion, pathogen, *Puccinia alli*, Fungicides, mancozeb, native, severity, effect

INTRODUCTION

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is a member of the Alliaceae family and is one of the most important vegetables in the world (Gambo et al., 2008; Messiaen, 1998). Onion is cultivated mainly for its bulb varies in size, shape and colour from which are derived phytochemicals that have important usage as human and animal medicines (Dawar et al., 2007). Used almost daily in every home it is an essential ingredient in Georgian diet. In Georgia, onion is produced in many parts of the country by small farmers, private growers and state enterprise. National production of onion is estimated to be over 19.2 thousand tons of dry bulb per annum and yield per hectare is 7.6 t ha⁻¹.

Despite onion is rapidly becoming the most popular vegetable among producers and consumers in Georgia, the present production level do not meet the demand of the country. Its productivity is also far below the level realized at global level (19.5 t ha⁻¹).

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Onion crop is vulnerable to infect by bacterial, viral, nematode and fungal diseases. Among them, diseases are the most damaging to onion crops.

Information on diseases of Onion is found in various works (Marziyeh et al., 2010; Hussain et al., 1977; Yohalem et al., 2003; Sang et al., 2014; Shainidze, 2014).

There are at least ten valid names for species of *Puccinia* and *Uromyces* that have been reported on species of *Allium* worldwide (Kato et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2012).

These rusts occurred in five clades. These five clades corresponded to (1) rusts on *A. porrum*, *A. ampeloprasum* and *A. fistulosum* from Europe, considered *Puccinia porri*; (2) rusts on *A. fistulosum* and *A. sativum* in Australia and China, considered *P. allii sensu lato*; (3) rusts on several species of *Allium* used in the study of Metcalf (2002), considered *P. allii sensu* (Gäumann, 1959); (4) specimens from the USA on *A. sativum* and *A. schoenoprasum* included in the study by (Anikster et al., 2004), considered *Puccinia allii sensu* (Koike et al., 2001), and (5) rusts on *A. schoenoprasum* from Europe and one specimen from Australia, considered *Puccinia mixta* (Dixon et al., 2010).

Among the rust, Onion rust, that can pose a high epidemic within a short period, is the major constraint in onion production areas in Georgia and is able to spread a long distance for infection. Accumulation of the pathogen causes severe bulb yield reduction due to the high density and even distribution on the host plants (Kanchaveli, 1980).

Several fungicides recommended for controlling these pathogens not only add up to human and environmental hazards but also be inconsistent and insufficient to deal with this disease.

However, management options, such as the use of resistant/tolerant onion varieties with supplementation of appropriate and compatible fungicides are recommended applicable management strategies for a long period production system of onion crop (Malik et al., 2017). Although the application of fungicides alone against onion rust is a common practice, the use of integrated management to subdue the disease through combination of various onion varieties along with compatible systemic fungicides is a more effective means than sole fungicide application. Therefore, integrated management of onion rust is the most efficient, environmentally sound and socially acceptable management strategy for sustainable onion crop production and productivity.

So far, management of the disease under irrigation and main rainy season production systems in all smallscale farmers have not been done in Adjara. Hence, finding an effective integrated management tactic for this particular disease is a prerequisite.

Therefore, the study was carried out with the objectives to evaluate the effects of host resistance, alone and alternate application of the different fungicides on onion rust epidemic and bulb yield; and determine the economics of fungicide application in the management of onion rust.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection: The experiment was carried of farmers' fields out at Khelvachauri and Keda (Adjara, Georgia) during 2019 and 2020 cropping seasons.

Isolation of fungi: For isolation of fungi from Brassica oleracea plants, the agar method was applied. Fungal pathogens were responsible for disease isolated from fruit. From the samples obtained, serial dilutions (1:10) were prepared in test tubes with 9 ml sterile water, adding 1 g of fruit samples until dilutions 10⁻⁵, 10⁻⁶ and 10⁻⁷, of which 50 μ L and shaken at 200 rpm for 3 hours. Samples collected were seeded by duplicate through diffusion technique on Petri dishes of 90 mm diameter containing one of the following artificial Potato Dextrose Aga (PDA) and Czapecks agar medium. After incubation (23°C for 6 days) the number for each fungus was calculated. All fungi were cultured using a single spore technique on PDA and Czapecks medium. After incubation, fungi were identified by their macroscopic and microscopic characteristics.

Identification of fungi: Fungal cultures identification was based on macroscopic characteristics like colony morphology, color, texture, shape and appearance were observed on potatodextrose agar (PDA) and microscopic characteristics like conidia shape, hyphal color, concentric zone, and pigmentation. Species identification was based on the morphological characteristics of single – spore isolates (Foster, et al., 2004).

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Collections of the fungi have been examined by standard light microscopy (Pereval, Carl Zeiss, Jena and Olympus, BX50, Hamburg, Germany). The SEM micrographs have been prepared by means of a JSM-35 (Japan) SEM microscope. The specimens examined were deposited at HAL, KW and TGM (Holmgren, et al., 1990).

Planting Materials and Fungicides: 3 onion varieties, namely Creole, Pinoy F1 and Enza (local control), all of which had different responses to onion rust, were used as varietal components of the experiment. Additionally, two commercially available and registered foliar fungicides were used for the experiment at the dose of manufacturers' recommendations. These fungicides were Mancozeb 75% WP, Diethane indofil M45 (2g/L), Nativo 75 WG (Water Dispersible Granule of 250 g kg⁻¹ Trifloxystrobin + 500 g kg⁻¹ Tebuconazole) and alteration of Mancozeb 75% WP and Nativo 75 WG, which were used alternatively or one after the other and alone.

Treatments, Experimental Design and Management Procedures:

The experiments consisted of 12 treatment combinations. A plot size of 2.5 m x 1.8 m area, and 0.3 m inter-rows and 0.1 m intra-plants spacing were used during the experiment. Plots and blocks were separated by 1.0 m and 1.5 m, respectively.

There were five rows of onion per plot and the plants were spaced at 0.25 m in each row. The central three rows were used as effective rows for data collection.

Applications of fungicides were done at starting from the onset of the first typical symptom of the disease. Four times spray frequencies of fungicides were employed at seven-day interval as used by Worku (2017). Onion were treated with Apron star prior to planting to prevent untargeted seedborne disease(s) as this fungicide is good for seed treatment and also effective for white rot disease management as suggested by Dilbo et al. (2015). Agronomic practices and regular monitoring were done uniformly to each experimental plot as recommended for the crop in the areas

Disease Assessment Disease Severity: Onion rust severity was recorded from 12 pre-tagged plants using systematically arranged pattern in the middle four rows of each plot starting from the first appearance of the disease symptoms. It was rated using a 0 to 9 disease scoring scale; where, 1 = no infections; 2 = 1-10% leaf area infected; 3 = 11- 20% leaf area infected; 4 = 21-30% leaf area infected; 5 = 31-40% leaf area infected; 6 = 41-50% leaf area infected; 7 = 51-60% leaf area infected; 8 = 61-70% leaf area infected; and 9 = 71-100% leaf area infected as described by Horneburg and Becker (2011). Disease severity scores were converted into percentage severity as follows.

$$\text{Disease Severity (\%)} = \frac{\text{Area of Diseased Tissue}}{\text{Total Tissue Area}} \times 100$$

The severity grades were converted into percentage severity index (PSI) for analyses as indicated by Wheeler (1969):

$$\text{PSI} = \frac{\text{Sum of numerical ratings}}{\text{No. of plants scored} \times \text{maximum disease score on scale}} \times 100$$

The relative disease severity reduction on untreated and treated plots of the treatment combination was calculated as follows.

$$\text{Relative disease severity reduction (\%)} = \frac{\text{untreated} - \text{treated}}{\text{untreated}} \times 100$$

Area under disease progress curve (AUDPC): It was also computed from PSI values for each plot as described by Campbell and Madden (1990).

$$\text{AUDPC} = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} 0.5 (X_i + X_{i+1}) (t_{i+1} - t_i)$$

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Where, n is the total number of disease assessments, t_i is the time of the i th assessment in days from the first assessment date and x_i is the PSI of disease at the i th assessment. AUDPC was expressed in %-days because severity (x) is expressed in percent and time (t) in days. Disease progress rate: Logistic, $\ln [(Y/1-Y)]$ (Van der Plank, 1963), and Gompertz, $-\ln[-\ln(Y)]$ (Berger, 1981) models were compared for estimation of disease progression rate from each treatment, and the Logistic model was found fit to the data. The goodness of fit of the models was tested based on the magnitude of the coefficient of determination (R^2). The transformed data of disease severity were regressed over time (DAT) to determine the model. The model was then used to determine the apparent rate of disease increase (r) and the intercept of the curve.

$$Y_t = \frac{1}{1 + \exp^{-1n[Y_0/(1-Y_0)] + rLt}}$$

Percentage fruit infection (PFI): It was recorded as percentage of tomato fruits infected per plant in the middle four rows as the average of 12 plants. Then the score was expressed as a percentage as follows:

$$PFI = \frac{\text{No. of fruits infected}}{\text{Total no. of fruits assessed}} \times 100$$

Assessment of Growth, Yield and Yield Related Traits: Important parameters like days to 50% flowering, days to 50% fruit setting, days to first and last picking, number of branches per plant, number of fruit clusters per plant, plant stand count, yield (t/ha) (marketable, unmarketable and total fruit yields) and single fruit weight (g) were collected.

Data Analysis: Data were analyzed following a procedure appropriate to the design of the experiment as described by Gomez and Gomez (1984) and logistic model and, general linear model (GLM) of SAS version 9.2 (SAS, 2009). The treatment means were separated using the least significant difference (LSD) test at 5% probability level. Correlation and regression analysis was used to determine the relationships between growth, yield and yield related traits, and disease severity and AUDPC across the treatments. It was performed to determine the association of disease parameters with yield obtained from the different fungicide schedules.

Relative yield loss and Yield increase in fruit yield: In addition to the above, relative yield loss from each plot was calculated using the formula suggested by Robert and James (1991):

$$\text{Relative\% yield loss} = \frac{Y_{bt} - Y_{lt}}{Y_{bt}} \times 100$$

Where, Y_{bt} is the yield of best treatment and Y_{lt} is the yield of lower treatments. At the same time, yield increase, and change in yield increase, over the untreated plots were obtained with the formula:

$$\text{Yield increase over the untreated check} = \frac{\text{Treated} - \text{Untreated}}{\text{Treated}} \times 100$$

Cost and Benefit Analysis: Cost and benefit of each treatment was analyzed using partially and marginal rate of return (MRR) as computed by considering the variable cost (fungicides and knapsack sprayer costs and cost of labor for fungicide applications) available for the respective treatment. Price of fruits, in \$, of each tomato variety per kilogram was obtained from the contemporary local market at harvest and total sale from one hectare were computed. Costbenefit analysis of each fungicide schedule was made to evaluate the economic benefits expected using the farm gate price of tomato at the time of harvest. Before applying the partial budget analysis (economic analysis) statistical analysis was done on the collected data to compare the average yields between each treatment to determine the economics of the disease management. With this, there were significance differences among the treatments. MRR was calculated using (CIMMYT, 1988):

$$MRR \% = \frac{DNI}{DIC} \times 100$$

Where, DNI = difference in net income compared with control, and DIC = difference in input cost compared with control. During cost benefit analysis using partial budget important points were considered; costs for all

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agronomic practices were uniform for all treatments; cost of labor and spraying equipment were taken based on the prevailing rates of payment in the locality; costs, return and benefit were calculated on hectare basis; and it is assumed that farmers produce this variety under integrated management of tomato late blight when the variety provided 100% marginal rate of returns.

RESULTS

On the Onion, 8 major species of Fungi (Onion rust - *Puccinia alli*, purple blotch - *Alternaria porri*, black mold diseases - *Aspergillus niger*, neck and bulb rot - *Botrytis alli*, onion twister - *Colletotrichum cingulata*, downy mildew - *Peronospora destructor*, pink rot - *Pyrenochaeta terrestris* and rot - *Fusarium oxysporium*) were identified as a result of phytopathological and mycological studies conducted in different places of agroecosis in Georgia.

Sometimes, during storage, the infected onion can be covered with a multi-colored mycelium which includes 6 species of fungi (*Mucor sp.*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Botrytis alli*, *Fusarium oxysporium*, *Alternaria spp.*, *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*).

Among the pathogens registered by us, onion rust *Puccinia alli*, are the most widespread and destructive pathogens of cultivated onion. Some disease, noresistant varieties onion, have been observed to dry (42 - 100%) out within a 3-4 day (Figure 1).

The initial symptom was small flecks, which expanded into slightly larger, oval- to diamond-shaped, reddish- to dull-orange pustules on the leaves. Reddish airborne spores (urediniospores) are produced copiously within the lesions. Later in the growing season, the lesions may appear dark because black survival spores (teliospores) develop within the pustules.

When the two cropping seasons were compared, the higher disease severity was recorded in 2020 than in 2019 cropping season. This variation in varietal responses to Onion rust might be due to genetic differences and epidemic differences between cropping seasons could be attributed to variability in weather variables during the experimental period since there was higher rainfall and relative humidity and lower aerial temperature in the growing period of 2020 than in 2019 cropping season.

Fig. 1. Affected organs (42 -100%) of onion in an untreated area

The average result for 2019-2020, obtained from the different onion varieties/fungicide application alone and in alternation had significant impacts on onion rust development. The treated with all treatments, that reflect on the increase in plant height, bulb diameter, bulb weight and total bulb yield compared with untreated after 90 days from sowing.

As shown in Table 1, show that in the experimental plot of Khelvachauri, treatment with the fungicide Mancozeb led to an increase in plant height (65.2 cm), bulb diameter (19.5 cm), bulb weight (123.0 g) on Pinoy F1. In the case of the use of other fungicides and other varieties of onions, these indicators change slightly.

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Plant height (51.0 cm), bulb diameter (13.5 cm), bulb weight (94.2 g) are significantly reduced in untreated areas. A similar result was obtained at the research site in Keda.

Table 1: Some plant growth parameters of onion of different control approaches after 90 days

Variety	Fungicide	Khelvachauri						Keda					
		Plant Height		Bulb diameter		Bulb weight		Plant Height		Bulb diameter		Bulb weight	
		(cm)	Increase (%)	(cm)	Increase (%)	(g)	Increase (%)	(cm)	Increase (%)	(cm)	Increase (%)	(g)	Increase (%)
Creole	Mancozeb	63.5	23.8	19.0	26.6	119.	27.3	62.1	22.8	17.3	25.6	120.	27.3
	Mancozeb+Nativo	61.2	20.2	18.6	23.0	0	25.3	61.3	21.2	16.6	22.0	0	25.3
	Nativo	55.4	18.0	17.2	22.8	118.	22.3	55.5	18.0	16.2	21.8	118.	22.3
	Nativo+Mancozeb	52.5	17.7	16.0	19.5	0	16.8	52.6	17.7	16.0	21.5	0	16.8
Pinoy F1	Mancozeb	65.2	25.6	19.5	26.7	123.	28.6	63.2	23.9	18.1	26.7	122.	26.4
	Mancozeb+Nativo	56.5	24.2	17.6	23.6	0	26.3	61.3	20.2	16.6	23.0	0	23.3
	Nativo	53.6	22.0	18.2	22.8	118.	23.3	55.5	8.0	18.2	22.7	117.	22.3
	Nativo+Mancoze	53.0	21.7	16.0	18.5	0	21.8	62.6	22.7	16.0	21.9	0	17.8
local (Enza)	Mancozeb	62.2	23.9	17.1	24.7	119.	23.4	63.2	23.9	17.1	26.7	120.	27.4
	Mancozeb+Nativo	61.3	20.2	16.6	22.0	0	23.3	61.3	20.2	16.6	23.0	0	25.3
	Nativo	55.5	18.0	16.2	19.8	118.	22.3	55.5	8.0	18.2	34.8	116.	22.3
	Nativo+Mancozeb	52.6	17.7	15.0	18.5	0	21.8	62.6	22.7	16.0	18.5	0	16.8
Untreated (control)	51.0	-	13.5	-	94.2	-	51	-	13.5	-	94.2	-	

Table 2 shows that onion rust was highly influenced by the application of Mancozeb and Nativo fungicides alone, in combination and in alternation. Interaction effects of onion variety x fungicide indicated that PSI at final assessment date, AUDPC and disease progress rate revealed a significant difference in both Khelvachauri and Kobuleti districts.

Analysis of variance revealed that there was an interaction effect of variety x fungicide for mean severity of onion rust at final date of assessment and they showed significant difference at both locations. The maximum (95.4%) mean severity was obtained on the untreated plots of the local cultivar and followed by untreated plots of Pinoy F1 and Creole varieties, which exhibited similar results with mean severity of 89.9% at 102 DAP at Khelvachauri. But, lower and insignificant mean severity was observed on the other treatments on the last assessment date in the same location at Khelvachauri.

Regarding Keda, the highest (83.4%) mean onion rust severity was recorded on the unsprayed plot of the Ensa cultivar, followed by Creole (76%) and Pinoy F1 (55%) at the last assessment date (92 DAP). With the same date of assessment, the lowest mean severity was recorded due to treatment with Mancozeb on plots of Pinoy F1 (5.7%) and Mancozeb + Nativo (5.4%).

The interaction effects of onion variety x fungicide application on AUDPC revealed significant difference among the evaluated treatments. The highest (2657.1 %-days) AUDPC value was recorded from untreated plots of all treatments at Khelvachauri. Untreated plots of Pinoy F1 and Creole varieties a non-significant difference; but, the treated Creole variety with Nativo differed significantly from Nativo and Mancozeb + Nativo treated Pinoy F1 variety.

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The treated local cultivar with Mancozeb, Nativo and their alternate applications showed a significant difference from the treated Pinoy F1 and Creole varieties and this had high AUDPC value. However, the fungicides Mancozeb, Nativo and their alternate applications on the Enza cultivar revealed nonsignificant difference among themselves. A similar phenomenon was depicted in Keda on tested onion varieties as well as the fungicides applied.

Table 2: Interaction effect of variety x fungicide on onion rust on final PSI and AUDPC at Khelvachauri and Keda districts of Adjara, during the 2019/2022 cropping season

Variety	Fungicide	Khelvachauri		Keda	
		PSI (f)	AUDPC	PSI (f)	AUDPC
Creole	Unsprayed	89.9 ^a	2281.8 ^b	76.00 ^a	1719.0 ^a
	Mancozeb	19.9 ^e	698.4 ^e	5.82 ^c	543.5 ^{bc}
	Mancozeb+Nativo	16.8 ^e	728.9 ^e	8.93 ^c	648.4 ^{bc}
	Nativo	18.7 ^e	773.0 ^e	12.15 ^c	681.8 ^{bc}
	Nativo+Mancozeb	16.8 ^c	833.9 ^e	20.03 ^c	768.7 ^{bc}
Pinoy F1	Unsprayed	90.2 ^a	2202.2 ^b	55.70 ^a	1393.1 ^a
	Mancozeb	18.58 ^e	636 ^e	5.70 ^e	584.5 ^{bc}
	Mancozeb+Nativo	19.41 ^e	835 ^e	5.43 ^e	505.2 ^{bc}
	Nativo	19.12 ^e	1038.8 ^e	17.62 ^e	778.9 ^{bc}
	Nativo+Mancozeb	18.23 ^e	743.3 ^c	7.33 ^e	609.0 ^{bc}
local (Enza)	Unsprayed	95.4 ^a	2657.1 ^a	83.4 ^a	1752.8 ^a
	Mancozeb	32.41 ^b	1719.2 ^c	7.21 ^c	548.3 ^{bc}
	Mancozeb+Nativo	33.85 ^b	1837 ^c	13.28 ^c	803.1 ^b
	Nativo	36.69 ^b	1858 ^c	17.35 ^c	801.2 ^b
	Nativo+Mancozeb	32.88 ^b	1921 ^c	8.56 ^c	574.2 ^{bc}
Means		36.9	1383	22.88	802.33
CV (%)		13.5	10.76	53.57	35.13
LSD (0.05)		8.3	246.21	20.46	467.17

Note: ^a PSI (f) = final percentage severity index at 102 DAP and 92 DAP in Lalibella and Gidan, respectively, AUDPC = Area under disease progress curve. CV = Coefficient of variation, LSD = Least significant difference at 0.05 level of probability.

Table 3 shows that among the sprayed treatments, Mancozeb alone fungicide application gave nil/minimum bulb yield losses. Relatively, the lower bulb yield losses were also obtained from plots sprayed with Nativo alone on Enza and Pinoy F1 onion varieties in both locations. However, total bulb yield losses were reduced by the application of alternate and alone fungicide application compared to the unsprayed check plots.

The highest (49.98%) relative bulb yield loss was obtained from unsprayed local cultivar that was higher by 4.55 and 11.54% from unsprayed Pinoy F1 and Creole, respectively, in Khelvachauri district. Similarly, maximum relative yield losses were calculated for the untreated Pinoy F1 (64.46%), Enza (63.92%) and Creole (63.32%) onion varieties in Keda district.

Table 3: Relative yield loss of onion due to onion rust (*P. allii*) as influenced by onion variety and fungicide application in Khelvachauri and Keda districts of Adjara, during the 2019 cropping season

Variety	Fungicide	Khelvachauri			Keda		
		Bulb yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Relative yield loss in percentage	Relative yield advantage in percentage	Bulb yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Relative yield loss in percentage	Relative yield advantage in percentage
Creole	Mancozeb	19.66	6.02	53.23	14.22	0.00	175.56
	Nativo +Mancozeb	18.28	11.77	43.64	8.88	37.55	72.09
	Nativo	17.66	0.00	63.01	10.88	23.49	110.85
	Nativo+Mancozeb	13.12	21.26	28.38	9.56	32.77	85.27
	Unsprayed	11.22	38.44	0.00	5.16	63.32	0.00
Pinoy F1	Mancozeb	21.12	0.00	82.70	14.44	0.00	183.12
	Mancozeb+Nativo	19.56	7.39	69.20	8.66	40.03	69.80
	Nativo	18.88	10.66	63.32	13.56	6.09	165.88
	Nativo+Mancozeb	18.88	10.66	63.32	12.96	10.66	152.92

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	Unsprayed	11.56	45.43	0.00	5.10	64.46	0.00
Enza (local cultivar)	Mancozeb	15.12	0.00	102.30	16.66	0.00	177.67
	Mancozeb+Nativo	13.34	46.30	8.62	8.88	46.70	48.00
	Nativo	12.88	39.01	23.37	10.22	38.66	70.33
	Nativo+Mancozeb	11.34	27.36	46.93	9.78	41.30	63.00
	Unsprayed	10.0	49.98	0.00	6.00	63.92	0.00

As can be seen from table 4, the maximum net profit was obtained on the onion varieties Pinoy F1 (16920 lari on 1 ha) and Creole (16000 lari on 1 ha) in combination with Mancozeb fungicide alone and on the variety Local only with Nativo (15620 lari on 1 ha). In case of alternate fungicide applications, higher marginal rate of return was noted than on unprotected plots. Especially treatment of Pinoy F1 and Local cultivar with Mancozeb+Nativo indicated higher marginal rate of return value than Nativo+Mancozeb and unsprayed plots.

Table 4. Partial budget analysis for the garlic rust management through host resistance, and alone and alternate applications of fungicides in Khelvachauri and Keda districts of Adjara, during the 2020 cropping season

Variety	Fungicide	Yield (t/ha ⁻¹)	Sale price (Lari kg ⁻¹)	Sale revenue (Lari)	Total input cost (Lari)	Net profit (Lari)
Creole	Mancozeb	16.0	1,0	16000	80	15920
	Nativo +Mancozeb	13.6	1,0	13600	69	13531
	Nativo	14.5	1,0	14500	58	14442
	Mancozeb+ Nativo	14.3	1,0	14300	69	14231
	Unsprayed	7.4	1,0	7400	0	7400
Pinoy F1	Mancozeb	17.0	1,0	17000	80	16920
	Nativo +Mancozeb	13.8	1,0	13800	69	13731
	Nativo	15.2	1,0	15200	58	15142
	Mancozeb+ Nativo	15.0	1,0	15000	69	14931
	Unsprayed	7.5	1,0	7500	0	7500
Enza (local cultivar)	Mancozeb	14.2	1,0	14200	58	14142
	Nativo +Mancozeb	13.5	1,0	13500	69	13431
	Nativo	15.7	1,0	15700	80	15620
	Mancozeb+ Nativo	13.9	1,0	13900	69	13831
	Unsprayed	7.2	1,0	7200	0	7200

Note: Mean unit of mean price of bulb per kilogram was \$ 0.33 (at the current exchange rate of 1\$ = 3.0 Lari) at the time of produce selling in 2019/20 cropping season.

DISCUSSION

Among the pathogens registered by us, onion rust *Puccinia allii*, are the most widespread and destructive pathogens of cultivated onion. Some disease, noresistant varieties onion, have been observed to dry (42 - 100%) out within a 3-4 day.

The initial symptom was small flecks, which expanded into slightly larger, oval- to diamond-shaped, reddish- to dull-orange pustules on the leaves. Reddish airborne spores (urediniospores) are produced copiously within the lesions. Later in the growing season, the lesions may appear dark because black survival spores (teliospores) develop within the pustules. The uredospores, teletospores and other taxonomic signs we have examined are the same as the data from different researchers (Yarwood and Gardner, 1941; Jennings et al., 1990 ; Schwartz and Mohan, 2008).

The results show that, the treated with all treatments, that reflect on the increase in plant height, bulb diameter, bulb weight and total bulb yield compared with untreated after 90 days from sowing. On the other hand, treated with fungicide the most effective on the growth parameters especially bulb weight and total bulb yield. These results are in harmony with obtained results of (Behroozin and Asad, 1994; Somkuwar et al., 1996).

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The analysis of variance revealed that the fungicides applied on the different onion varieties showed significant interaction effect that resulted in the lowest final severity of onion rust in both Khelvachauri and Keda districts. The fungicide-treated Pinoy F1 and Creole varieties manifested very low final severity, which was less by 15% than the protected local cultivar. The low disease severity might be attributed to the fungicides Mancozeb and Nativo alone, which are the most effective systemic fungicides that interfere with and inhibit the growth and reproduction of the fungus. In this regard, the variety Pinoy F1 and Creole might have a better response/resistance level to rust disease than the local cultivar. The highest final severity of onion rust was recorded from the plots of untreated local and both improved garlic varieties, which had a significant impact on bulb yield and yield-related components in both districts. The highest onion rust severity in the untreated plots was attributed to undisturbed and continuous uredospore germination in that specific host ranges. This current finding is in agreement with the observation of Worku (2017) who reported that high (83%) garlic rust severity had been recorded in the untreated garlic crop in Ethiopia.

Integration of different onion varieties and fungicide sprays lowered disease progress rates at both experimental sites.

The highest disease progress rates were recorded due to heavy infection by onion rust on all unprotected onion varieties, while the onion varieties treated with Mancozeb, Nativo and their alternate sprays resulted in minimum disease progress rates during the study. Thus, the fungicides Mancozeb and Nativo exhibited adverse and antagonistic effects on onion rust physiology since they suppressed and prohibited further lesion expansions.

The main effect of onion varieties and fungicide applications showed a significant difference in marketable bulb yield, while their interaction effect revealed a non-significant difference. An average (17 t ha⁻¹) bulb yield of Pinoy F1 was significantly higher than the remaining onion varieties. This could be accounted for its innate genetic potential being recently improved and have also best field performance during the field experiment with respect to plant height, number of leaves per plant, bulb weights and diameters, especially in Khelvachauri Reasonable onion bulb yield was obtained on all the treated-plots since the alternate and alone fungicide applications could enhance growth parameters and suppressed disease progression at both testing locations. This is in line with the finding of Worku (2017) who stated that the application of systemic fungicides could suppress further uredospore proliferation, uredia expansion and enhance bulb yield. On the other hand, marketable bulb yield of onion was highly penalized in unprotected-plots of all onion varieties. This might be attributed to weighty infection and the contagious nature of the pathogen in unprotected check plots.

The budget analysis also confirmed that application of Mancozeb and Nativo fungicides alone were the most cost effective and efficient towards onion rust management option. Comparatively, maximum net benefit and marginal rate of return resulted from Mancozeb and Nativo fungicide applications in comparison with all other alternate and control fungicide applications in both districts. Hence, solely application of Mancozeb and Nativo for the management of onion rust on the moderately resistant and susceptible varieties was the relatively more profitable and economically acceptable fungicides than other treatments.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Onion rust (*Puccinia alli*) is known as one of production-limiting biotic agent in the world and in Georgia. The current research was carried out of farmers' fields out at Khelvachauri and Keda (Adjara, Georgia) during 2019 and 2020 cropping seasons.

On the Onion, 8 major species of Fungi were identified as a result of phytopathological and mycological studies conducted in different places of agroecosystem in Georgia. Among the pathogens registered by us, onion rust *Puccinia alli*, are the most widespread and destructive pathogens of cultivated onion.

Average result for 2019-2020, obtained from the different onion varieties/fungicide application alone and in alternation had significant impacts on onion rust development.

The results show that, the treated with all treatments, that reflect on the increase in plant height, bulb diameter, bulb weight and total bulb yield compared with untreated after 92-102 days from sowing.

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The obtained data show that treated with fungicide Mancozeb caused increase of plant height (62.5 cm), bulb diameter (25.6 cm), bulb weight (123.0 g) on Pinoy F1 compared with other fungicide treatments while, the treated with Nativo+Mancozeb decreased the bulb diameter (15.2 cm), bulb weight (29.2 g) and total bulb yield, compared with untreated after 90 days from sowing.

It was established that onion rust was highly influenced by the application of Mancozeb and Nativo fungicides alone, in combination and in alternation.

Analyses of variance revealed that interaction effects of Mancozeb, Nativo, and their alternate applications with Pinoy F1 and Creole varieties showed the lowest disease severity, area under the disease progress curve, and disease progress rate as compared to the unsprayed plots of all varieties. The variety Pinoy F1 showed significantly higher (21.1 t ha⁻¹) yield and, exhibited 1.4 t and 6.0 t yield advantages over Creole variety and the local cultivar, respectively.

The economic analysis also confirmed that sole application of Mancozeb on Pinoy F1 and Nativo on both Creole and Enza showed higher net profit and marginal rates of return than other treatment combinations.

Thus, the fungicides Mancozeb and Nativo alone were relatively effective against onion rust and economically profitable in Adjara and related agro-ecologies for the variety Pinoy F1. However, there was no significant variation in onion bulb yield of all varieties in Adjara, and the same fungicides with onion variety can be used for rust management and sustainable onion production.

Therefore, integrated management practices must be adopted by all onion growers, including small household farmers, private investors, and state enterprises, for curbing the development of rust and for sustainable onion production in the study area and in other areas with similar agro-ecologies that favour tomato late blight epidemics. Also, further extensive studies are recommended for evaluation of additional onion varieties and management options under different agro-ecological conditions to come up with suitable conclusive management options and to enhance high quality tomato production in the study areas and elsewhere in Adjara having similar agro-ecologies.

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